

INFLUENCE OF HALAL PRODUCT, GREEN MARKETING, AND INFORMATION ADOPTION TO SERVICE QUALITY ON CUSTOMER LOYALTY AND CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AT STARBUCKS COFFEE BANDUNG, INDONESIA

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Abstract

Starbucks Coffee is one of the businesses that implements a green marketing strategy. Consumers not only look at a product in terms of quality, brand and price, but consumers also look at the product attached to the product. This research aims to determine the influence of halal products, green marketing, and information adaptation, purchase decisions, customer satisfaction on customer loyalty through customer satisfaction as an intervening variable. The method used in this research is quantitative with descriptive and causality research as well as the SEM-PLS analysis method. The sampling technique used was a nonprobability sampling technique with a total sample of 386 Starbucks Coffee customers in Bandung City. Result showed that Halal Products have a positive and significant effect on Purchase Decisions. Green marketing has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Decisions. Information Adaption has a positive and significant effect on Purchase. Purchase Decision has a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction. Customer Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Customer Loyalty among Starbucks Coffee customers in Bandung City.

Keywords: Halal Product, Green Marketing, Information Adaption, Purchase Decision, Customer Loyalty, Customer Satisfaction.

1. INTRODUCTION

Earth is a habitat and residence for various living creatures in the world, including humans. However, the earth is getting hotter day by day due to global warming. Global warming can result in natural disasters, which means disasters on earth. There are several causes of global warming, namely an increase in Sea Surface Temperature (SST), the heat of the earth, the heat of the air, but SST is one of the important things because it is an indicator of climate change, so all the factors that cause global warming need to be detected early. as a prevention of disasters that are detrimental to humanity (Dohong, 2020). Some of the causes of global warming are lifestyle, consumption patterns and irregular population growth, coupled with various human activities which sometimes damage the environment, one of which is waste.

The waste problem is an unfinished problem in Indonesia, increasing population will increase the volume of waste. The composition of waste produced from human activities means 60-70% organic waste and 30-40% non-organic waste, meanwhile the second largest composition of non-organic waste, namely 14%, is plastic waste. One of the most abundant types of plastic waste is plastic packaging. Jambeck, 2015 stated that Indonesia is ranked second in the world

after China, producing 187.2 million tons of plastic waste in the waters. This is related to data from the Ministry of Environment and Forestry which revealed that plastic waste from 100 shops or members of the Indonesian Retail Entrepreneurs Association (APRINDO) in just 1 year alone had reached 10.95 million plastic waste. This amount is equivalent to an area of 65.7 hectares of plastic. This is considered to reduce global warming and have a negative impact on biological health and climate change. (Ambari, 2020; Browne et al., 2013). Specifically, the Indonesian Central Statistics Agency in 2021 explained that in 2021 Indonesia would produce approximately 66 million tons of plastic per year. This condition is projected that in 2025 approximately 9 million tons of plastic waste will be obtained per day (BPS, 2019). The ignorant behavior of people who exploit the environment to meet their needs results in large-scale plastic waste pollution and ultimately results in climate change and hampers harmony in the environment (Dohong, 2020; Chandra, 2020). This situation shows that the majority of waste contributors are in the culinary and beverage industry (Rasyadi, 2019).

The significant increase in the food and beverage industry has certainly led to an increasingly high growth in the amount of plastic waste because the industry continues to depend on single-use plastic packaging. This situation ultimately encourages more and more businesses to strive to exploit the potential of environmental awareness for business operations in response to growing public concern for the environment by starting to market products or services that are healthier for customers and environmentally friendly. The company's efforts to apply environmental problems to its marketing activities have led to a new phenomenon in the form of the green marketing concept. Green marketing is a company strategy to market products using environmentally friendly methods in marketing activities, such as modifying products, changing packaging, adjusting production processes, and even updating promotional methods (Sandeen, 2009; Irkhamni et al., 2017). This strategy is considered to be able to help companies create a competitive advantage by creating an 'environmentally friendly' image in consumer perceptions thereby increasing customer loyalty (Sari & Setiawan, 2017).

Green marketing is the newest trend and is currently developing. This allows comfort and safety for humans, animals and plants. The term green marketing began to appear in the late 1980s to early 1990s. The American Marketing Association (AMA) held the first seminar on "Ecological Marketing" in 1975. The results of the seminar published the first book on green marketing with the same title as the seminar's theme. Another term that is often used is environmental marketing. All countries in the world are starting to take important steps to reduce the amount of plastic used and implement environmentally friendly products in an effort to preserve the earth. It is hoped that these products will not have an excessive impact on the environment and will also be able to convert waste into items that can be reused. So, this effort is able to save the earth and living creatures from excess waste (Rajeshkumar, 2012).

One of the world companies that is aggressively implementing the green marketing concept is Starbucks. For example, the go green program launched by Starbucks is providing a 10% discount for visitors who bring their own drink bottles/cups when enjoying coffee from Starbucks. By involving visitors in the re-use movement or reuse of used coffee cups, this company can reduce 109 coffee cup waste trucks every year (Neviana, 2010).

Apart from that, Starbucks also carries out creative promotions promoting green concerns through the "Starbucks tumbler on the go" program. This program was carried out with the aim of educating and changing the consumption behavior of Starbucks consumers from consuming Starbucks beverage products in regular disposable glass packaging to consumers' personal tumbler glass packaging which can be purchased at Starbucks outlets.

The Starbucks company's "go green" image is created through its commitment to waste disposal and the use of appropriate materials. Starbucks utilizes campaign tools by teaching customers the right ways to reuse, reduce and recycle product packaging. This research seeks to see how Starbucks' Green Marketing influences its Green Brand Image, which in turn influences customer Purchase Intention.

This research focuses on Starbucks in Bandung City due to several considerations. First, Starbucks Coffee is one of the companies that implements a green marketing strategy and is known for its contribution to the environment such as perfect waste disposal, reducing disposable cups/cups, and changing packaging to use tumblers to minimize and recycle food packaging. 2nd, Coffee Shops in Bandung City are growing very rapidly, especially Starbucks Coffee which has 17 branches in Bandung City from the 500 largest outlets throughout Indonesia, with this phenomenon making it easier for companies to provide awareness and education about their environmentally friendly products to consumers.

Wicaksana's research findings (2014) assess that Starbucks customer loyalty in Bandung City has a high percentage and is categorized as satisfied buyers. The following are the locations of Starbucks outlets in Bandung.

Apart from implementing green marketing, customer loyalty for company products can be created through providing quality service (Zeithaml et al., 1996; Kotler & Keller, 2016). Customer loyalty is formed when a company provides quality value (Parasuraman et al., 1985; Kotler & Armstrong, 2017).

The establishment of quality money service by companies in today's competitive environment is an important strategy for the success and sustainability of the company and ultimately can build high customer loyalty. The final factor identified as influencing consumers to become loyal comes from customer satisfaction.

Customer satisfaction is an assessment of the services provided by consumers according to the quality of service and customer experience when purchasing goods or services (Kotler & Armstrong, 2017; Tjiptono, 2014). It is indicated that achieving the level of customer satisfaction is also influenced by the green marketing strategy or service quality implemented by the company.

This is a consequence of consumer behavior which often compares the expectations that customers have and want to fulfill with the performance of the services provided by the company to fulfill these expectations (Fida et al., 2020; Malau, 2017). If customers feel satisfaction regarding using aspects of green marketing or service quality, consumers are considered to be loyal and willing to make repeat purchase transactions at the company.

Several Starbucks outlets in the city of Bandung still have many complaints from their customers. Judging from Figure 1.3, customer complaints about Starbucks service quality. For example, the atmosphere is unpleasant in several places, the service from the baristas is less friendly and slow in completing orders, the quality of the coffee is still lacking, and Wi-Fi problems often occur at several Starbucks in Bandung.

The service provided does not match the expectations that customers should get. Apart from that, based on the "Google Review" survey, Starbucks in Bandung only has a rating of 4.5 - 4.6 which is considered good but is still inferior to several outlets outside Bandung which have a rating of 4.6 - 4.7 by providing good quality service. Good and quality. Service quality is the fulfillment of customer needs and desires and the accuracy of delivery to match customer expectations. Thus, there are two main factors that influence service quality, namely expected service and perceived service (Tjiptono 2002, p.59).

Apart from paying attention to product quality, due to the many complaints from Starbucks customers, they should pay attention to service quality. fair and correct service quality provided by employees who consider the service they receive to be the same or even better than expected, makes consumers feel satisfied and become loyal to the service provided.

The service quality factor needs to continue to be improved and even improved so that you feel satisfied when provided with service by Starbucks Coffee. Service quality starts with customer needs, customer satisfaction and ends with Starbucks customer loyalty.

As a result, quality products and services play an important role in creating customer satisfaction which can bring several benefits to Starbucks, including a positive impact on customer loyalty, the potential to become a source of future income, reducing transaction costs with customers in the future, reducing volatility, increasing price tolerance., increase positive verbal recommendations, customers are more open, increase the relative negotiation power of the company towards the network of suppliers, business partners and distribution channels (Tjiptono, 2011: 288).

In order to obtain customer loyalty, there is no other strategy except by trying to provide maximum customer satisfaction, while the level of customer satisfaction will be influenced by service quality. Apart from influencing customer satisfaction, service quality will also influence customer loyalty, this was stated by Parasuraman et.al, (1985).

From the explanation above, it can be seen that environmental damage and industrial development are faster. For this, consumers need awareness of the importance of choosing or buying environmentally friendly products. Starbucks has implemented the green marketing concept by recycling its cups to be used as packaging for coffee drinks, using proper water, etc.

By identifying green marketing and service quality variables on customer loyalty with customer satisfaction as an intervening variable, and to find out the effectiveness of green marketing for Starbucks and whether this results in a real improvement in the company.

Problem Formulation

Formulation of the problem in the research to be studied:

- 1) Is there a significant influence of halal product image on Starbucks Coffee purchase decisions?
- 2) Is there a significant influence of green marketing on Starbucks Coffee purchase decisions?
- 3) Is there a significant influence of information adaptation on Starbucks Coffee purchase decisions?
- 4) Is there a significant influence of purchase decisions on Starbucks Coffee customer satisfaction
- 5) Is there a significant influence of customer satisfaction on Starbucks Coffee customer loyalty?

Purpose of the Paper

From problem formulation that has been described, the objectives of this research are:

- 1) To determine the significant influence of halal product image on Starbucks Coffee purchase decisions
- 2) To determine the significant influence of green marketing on Starbucks Coffee purchase decisions
- 3) To determine the significant influence of information adaptation on Starbucks Coffee purchase decisions
- 4) To determine the significant influence of purchase decisions on Starbucks Coffee customer satisfaction
- 5) To determine the significant influence of customer satisfaction on Starbucks Coffee customer loyalty

Benefits of research

The benefits of this research are divided into two uses, namely theoretical and practical uses, as follows:

Theoretical Benefits

Providing information in the field of marketing, especially regarding the influence of green marketing and service quality on customer loyalty, as well as the influence of the intervening variable on customer satisfaction. Apart from that, it is hoped that this research is intended to serve as a guide for future researchers in the same field.

Practitioner Benefits

- a. It is hoped that this research can provide many new lessons for the author himself, especially how to implement the theories obtained in lectures, which are written in the form of scientific research, so that in the end it is useful and good.
- b. This research is expected to provide benefits for the company that is used as the object of the case study in improving company performance and strategy which is expected to have a positive impact in the form of increasing company profits.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Halal Brand Image

Halal Brand Image is the positive perception that Muslim consumers have towards a brand due to the brand's compliance with Islamic principles and values, especially related to the consumption of halal products Raza et al., (2021).

According to research conducted by Ali et al., (2020) In the construction concept of halal food branding, for example, if the halal brand image is a node in consumer memory, then branding constructions such as perceived brand quality, brand satisfaction, brand trust and brand loyalty can is another important node related to this matter. Halal brand image node.

This means that these constructs (perceived brand quality, brand satisfaction, brand trust and brand loyalty) function as associations towards the halal brand image. According to research conducted by Wardi et al., (2022) defines Halal Brand Image as "Muslim consumers' overall impression and perception of a brand which is formed by the brand's conformity with halal principles and the brand's commitment to providing halal products and services." This definition emphasizes that the Halal Brand Image includes the overall impression or perception of Muslim consumers towards the brand, which is formed from the brand's conformity with halal principles and the brand's commitment to providing halal products and services. Meanwhile, research conducted by Ali et al., (2020) defines Halal Brand Image as a brand image based on consumer perceptions of brand compliance with Islamic law and principles in the production and delivery of products or services.

2.2 Green Marketing

According to Tsiotsou & Ratten, (2014) marketing is an approach to marketing that focuses on environmentally friendly products and services. The main goal of green marketing is to reduce the negative impact of products and business activities on the natural environment, as well as promote sustainable practices.

Then finally, the Environmental definition, namely green marketing, is an effort made by an organization to produce, promote, package and claim products in a way that is very sensitive or responsive to ecological concerns. According to Tsiotsou & Ratten, (2019), green marketing is defined as a holistic and responsible strategic management process that identifies, anticipates and meets stakeholder needs that do not affect human or environmental welfare.

2.3 Information Adaptation

According to Shen et al., (2014) the information adoption model is used to describe the process of how information can be adopted by people and influence their behavior and intentions through computer-based communication. Information adaptation is a combination of the Technology Acceptance Model and the Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM). Then Wijaya & Septianto, (2018) proposed to integrate these three models and create an IAM (information adaptation) model. According to Nguyen-Viet, (2023) the IAM model is very applicable to eWOM studies because this model addresses information on communication platforms mediated by personal computers. Information adoption is considered another factor that may influence consumer purchase intentions. Consumers who engage and adopt e-WOM information are more likely to have purchase intentions.

2.4 Customer Satisfaction (Customer Satisfaction)

According to Irawan et al., (2021), "Customer satisfaction occurs if the perceived performance is greater than expectations, then the customer will feel satisfied, and if the perceived performance value is smaller than expectations then the customer will not feel satisfied."

Meanwhile, according to Kotler & Armstrong in Maramis et al., (2018), consumer satisfaction is the extent to which product performance responses meet buyer expectations.

According to Giese and Cote in Chiu et al., (2019), customer satisfaction is:

- 1) Summary of various active response intensities. A researcher must define explicitly, a consumer who experiences a type of effective response and a high level of intensity.
- 2) Within a specific determination time and limited duration. A researcher must be able to estimate the duration of the response, including determining the time that is most relevant in solving the research problem.
- 3) Which is aimed at important aspects in obtaining and/or consuming products. Researchers must identify the research focus based on the research question or managerial problem at hand.

2.6 Customer Loyalty

Loyalty is literally defined as fidelity, namely a person's loyalty to an object. Loyalty is a condition where customers have a positive attitude towards a brand, are committed to that brand, and intend to continue purchasing in the future. This means that loyalty is always related to customer preferences and purchases Candiwan & Wibisono, (2021).

According to Kotler & Armstrong, (2016), consumer loyalty is more associated with behavior than with attitude. If someone is a loyal consumer, the consumer will show purchasing behavior which is defined as non-random purchases expressed from time to time by several decision-making units.

2.7 Hypothesis Development

2.7.1 The relationship between Halal product image and purchase decisions

Products whose packaging is labeled halal will emotionally influence consumers that the product is safe and free from risk which then influences them in the purchasing decision process (Elliott, 2015). Lutfie et al (2016) stated that products that have a halal label on their packaging can add value to the brand image of the product. The research results of Anggadwita, Dini and Veland (2019) show that the halal label significantly influences the product's brand image value. The halal label is a factor that is considered in the purchasing decision process. Clear product information will make consumers make purchases without hesitation (Kotler, 2005). Increasing public awareness regarding the halal label has an impact on their decisions to purchase products and services (Anggadwita, Dini and Veland, 2019). Maulidiyah et al (2019) and Simbolon (2019) also stated that halal labels influence consumer purchasing decisions.

2.7.2 The relationship between green marketing and purchase decisions

Several previous studies have shown that there is a positive and significant influence between green marketing and purchase decisions. One of them is research conducted by Govender & Govender (2016). In this research it was proven that green marketing has a positive effect on purchase decisions. The same results were also found in different areas with different research subjects. Research conducted by Putra & Gumanti (2017) also showed that green marketing had a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions. Research conducted by Dwipamurti et al. (2018) also show that green marketing has a positive effect on purchase decisions. Based on several previous studies, it is stated that there is a positive and significant relationship between green marketing and purchase decisions.

2.7.3 Relationship between Information Adaptation and Purchase Decision

Information reception is explained by Shen, Zheng, and Zhao (2014) as the process of internalizing information by recipients as well as receiving information from external sources, which includes how the information helps them gain knowledge and improve their decision-making process. Previous research has shown that information usefulness influences information acceptance. This phenomenon is often observed and analyzed in the context of its influence on purchase intentions. Acceptance of information occurs after they receive and use the information in the purchasing decision making process Ismagilova et al., (2017). The information reception model is generally utilized to develop a better understanding of how intentions are formed through messages received through eWorm communications Sardar et al, (2021). Kemp (2020) explains that purchase intention arises between the evaluation stage and purchasing decision making, when consumers make brand ratings and preferences. Flow is then formed after consumers adopt the information in the purchasing decision making process, so that this can influence their considerations which ultimately leads to purchase intentions. Erkan and Evans (2016) developed a hypothesis where consumers who adopt eWOM information are more likely to have purchase intentions, which was later proven to be supported.

2.7.4 Relationship between purchase decisions and customer satisfaction

According to research conducted by Kotler & Armstrong, (2018) said that customer satisfaction is closely related to purchasing decisions. If customers are satisfied with the product or service they purchased, they are more likely to make repeat purchases in the future. the relationship between product quality, customer trust, and customer loyalty. They concluded that more positive purchasing decisions tend to trigger higher customer satisfaction, and this will contribute to long-term customer loyalty.

2.7.5 The relationship between customer satisfaction and customer loyalty

According to Kotler & Armstrong, (2018), they state that "The best approach to retaining customers is to provide high satisfaction and value, which results in customer loyalty." This means that providing a high level of satisfaction and value to customers can generate loyalty from those customers. Meanwhile, Haryono (2016) believes that the satisfaction felt by consumers when using a product or service has implications for loyal attitudes towards the product or service, as long as the product or service meets their expectations. In this context, the opinions of these two experts can be strengthened by previous research conducted by Espejel (2007), which was mentioned in Haryono's (2016) article. This research found that consumer satisfaction has a positive and significant influence on consumer loyalty.

2.8 Framework of Thought

The rationale is a part of the research that describes the researcher's thinking. According to (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016) states that a framework is a conceptual model of how a theory relates to various factors called important problems. Meanwhile, according to Sapto Haryoko, quoted from (Hair et al., 2019), a research framework is needed if the research involves two or more variables. So this research framework is based on several factors that emerged from several previous studies. These factors are Halal product image, Green marketing, Information adaptation, Purchase decision, Customer satisfaction, and Customer loyalty. Thus, the framework of thought resulting from this research can be described as follows:

Figure 2.1: Framework of Thought

2.9 Research Hypothesis

The research hypothesis is a temporary answer to the problem formulation (Sugiyono, 2017: 105). This is because the evidence is based on existing theory and is not derived empirically from a collection of survey distribution data. This is in the form of a statement regarding the relationship between two or more variables based on the framework of thought that has been described. Based on the framework above, the hypothesis that will be proposed and proven to be true is:

- 1) There is a significant influence of halal product image on Starbucks Coffee purchase decisions
- 2) There is knowledge of the significant influence of green marketing on Starbucks Coffee purchase decisions
- 3) There is knowledge of the significant influence of information adaptation on Starbucks Coffee purchase decisions
- 4) There is knowledge of the significant influence of purchase decisions on Starbucks Coffee customer satisfaction
- 5) There is a significant influence of customer satisfaction on Starbucks Coffee customer loyalty

3. METHODS

Research methods are procedures for conducting research (Hasan I.I., 2002). As a research method, quantitative research methods were used in this research. In addition, this method is described as a quantitative method based on positivist philosophy, which studies a certain population or sample, uses research tools in data collection and quantitative/statistical data analysis, and aims to test predetermined hypotheses (Sugiyono, 2017).

This research is conclusive in its objective (cause-effect). The aim of this research is to analyze causality where changes in one variable cause changes in other variables without side effects (Indrawan & Yuniawati, 2017).

This research includes correlational research. Correlational research is a type of research where the researcher aims to describe important variables related to the research question (Indrawati, 2015), and this research also does not interfere with the data.

Meanwhile, this research is a cross-sectional study in relation to the research period. Cross Sectional Research is research designed to collect data in order to process, analyze and draw conclusions over a certain period of time (Indrawati, 2015, p. 118).

Table 3.1: Operasional Variable

Variable	Dimensions	Item Indikator	Questionnaire Instrument Items
Halal product Image Ali et al., (2020)	Brand Quality	X1.1	The Starbucks coffee brand is currently the best benchmark for halal commitment
	Brand Trust	X1.2	The Starbucks coffee brand is currently well known among halal milk brands
	Brand Satisfaction	X1.3	The Starbucks coffee brand currently answers all my halal problems
	Brand Loyalty	X1.4	The Starbucks Coffee brand can now be trusted regarding its halal promise
Green Marketing (Manongko, 2018)	Environmental Attitude	X2.1	I feel that Starbucks Coffee understands the importance of reducing plastic waste and is taking steps to reduce it.
	Environmental Concern	X2.2	I feel very concerned about the reduction in single-use plastic carried out by Starbucks Coffee
	Perceived Seriousness of Environmental	X2.3	I believe that Starbucks Coffee views the problem of ocean plastic pollution as a serious threat.
	Perceived Environmental Responsibility	X2.4	I believe that Starbucks Coffee has a responsibility to support sustainable policies related to natural resources.
	Perceived Effectiveness of Environmental Behavior	X2.5	I believe that Starbucks Coffee has a responsibility to support sustainable policies related to natural resources.
	Perceived Self-Image in Environmental Protection	X2.6	I feel that being a customer who supports sustainable business practices at Starbucks Coffee has had a positive impact on how I view myself
	Peer Influence	X2.7	I believe that the experiences and stories of my friends at Starbucks Coffee provide inspiration for better environmental action.
Information Adaption (Shen et al., 2014)	Shopping experience	X3.1	When I want to shop, I will consider the shopping experience using social media.
	Information Recommendations	X3.2	I will ask for recommendations from other users on social media before I go shopping
	Buying decision	X3.3	I am willing to buy products recommended by other users on social media
Purchase Decision Kotler & Armstrong, (2016)	Product selection	X4.1	I tend to choose products with a good brand reputation.
	Brand choice	X4.2	I tend to choose products that offer the best value for the price
	Purchase amount	X4.3	I am more interested in brands that have a variety of product choices
	Payment method	X4.4	Various payment methods at Starbucks Coffee
	Purchase time	X4.5	Limited time to purchase at Starbucks Coffee

	Choice of dealer	X4.6	I tend to buy products that have positive reviews from other users
Customer Satisfaction Irawan, (2019)	Feeling of Satisfaction	X5.1	I am satisfied with the quality of the products and services provided
	loyalty	X5.2	I always buy Starbucks coffee products
	Customer satisfaction	X5.3	I feel satisfied with Starbucks coffee products and services
	Recommendation	X5.4	I often recommend Starbucks coffee products to my relatives
Cuatomer Loyalty Su et al., (2022)	Repeat purchase	Y.1	I always repurchase Starbucks coffee products
	Habit	Y.2	I often consume products from Starbucks
	Sure it's the best brand	Y.3	I believe Starbucks Coffee is the best coffee brand
	Still choose that brand	Y.4	Even though other coffee shops offer the same product, I still choose Starbucks coffee
	Love the brand	Y.5	I like the Starbucks coffee brand
	Recommendation	Y.6	I would recommend this brand/company to friends and family.

According to Sugiyono (2018:92) A measurement scale is an agreement that becomes a reference for determining the length and shortness of the interval in a measuring instrument, so that the measuring instrument produces quantitative data at the time of measurement.

The measurement of each variable in this study uses an ordinal measurement scale. According to Sugiyono (2018:92) an ordinal scale is a measurement scale that not only determines categories but also determines the ranking of the construct being measured. Ordinal scales further differentiate categories to provide information about how respondents differentiate categories by assessing their levels.

The instrument scale used in this research is the Likert scale. According to (Hasan, 2002), the Likert scale is a type of scale used to measure research variables (certain social phenomena) such as attitudes, opinions and social perceptions of a person or group of people.

The Likert scale is an extension of the assessment scale, this scale is usually used specifically to measure attitudes, opinions and written observations (questionnaires) of people or groups subject to attitudes or treatment (Indrawan and Yaniawati, 2017).

After the variable measurement model has been assessed, the next step is to evaluate the structural model or inner model. First, evaluate the structural model by looking at the importance of the relationship between constructs/variables.

This can be seen from the path coefficient which describes the strength of the relationship between structures. The sign or direction on the path (path coefficient) must follow the hypothesis theory, meaning that it can be seen in the t-test obtained from this process. Which is obtained from the bootstrapping process or resampling method (Haryono, 2017).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondent characteristics are all respondent identities that are considered relevant to the problems identified. Below are the characteristics of respondents based on gender, age, highest level of education and length of service.

Table 5: Characteristics of Respondents

Gender	Frequency	%
Male	165	43,5%
Female	221	56,5%
Total	386	100%
Age	Frequency	%
< 20 Year	2	0,5%
20 - 25 Year	201	52%
26 - 30 Year	160	41,4%
31 - 35 Year	20	5,18%
> 35 Year	3	0,8%
Total	386	100%
Education	Frequency	%
High School	1	0,3%
DIPLOMA (D3/D4)	271	70,4%
Bachelor	22	5,2%
Postgraduate	92	24,2%
Total	386	100%

Source: 2023 questionnaire data processing

Table 5 above is a recapitulation of respondent characteristics based on gender. From this table it is known that the majority of the respondents studied were 57% women and the remaining 44% were men. So it can be seen that the majority of respondents studied were women.

This is in accordance with research conducted by Muhammad Hanif (2020) which states that women visit Starbucks more and use various types of transactions than men. If we look at age as shown in table 5 above, it can be seen that half of the respondents studied were aged between 22-24 years as much as 50.0% and very few of the respondents were aged more than 24 years as much as 1.0% and those aged less than 18 years are only 0.3%. So it can be seen that half of the respondents studied were aged between 22-24 years.

This is in accordance with research conducted by Novita Nurul (2020) which states that 22-24 year olds buy Starbucks the most. If we look at their final education as shown in table 5 and figure above, it can be seen that the majority of the respondents studied had a recent education of 71% and very few of the respondents had an elementary/middle school education, only 0.3%. So it can be seen that the majority of the respondents studied had at least a high school education. This is in accordance with research conducted by Sakswita (2017) which states that Starbucks visitors are dominated by those with a high school education.

4.1 SEM-PLS Verification Analysis

In structural equation modeling there are two types of models formed, namely the measurement model (outer model) and the structural model (inner model). The measurement model explains the proportion of variance of each manifest variable (indicator) that can be explained in the latent variable. Through the measurement model, it will be known which indicators are in the domain of forming latent variables. After the measurement model for each latent variable has been described, the next step is to describe the structural model which will examine the influence of each exogenous latent variable on the endogenous latent variable, using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) using the Partial Least Square approach (PLS) v4.0.

4.1.1 Testing the Measurement Model (Outer Model)

Measurement model testing (outer model) is used to determine the specifications of the relationship between latent variables and manifest variables. This test includes convergent validity, discriminant validity and reliability tests. The measurement model explains the proportion of variance of each manifest variable (indicator) that can be explained in the latent variable. Through the measurement model, it will be known which indicators are in the domain of forming latent variables. After the measurement model for each latent variable is described, the structural model is then described which will examine the influence of each exogenous latent variable. The outer model in this research can be seen in the following figure based on the Algorithm results:

Figure 3: Outer model Structural Equation Modeling (Algorithm)

Source: SmartPLS Version 4.0 Output Results

4.1.2 Convergent Validity

Convergent Validity relates to the principle that the manifest variables of a construct should be highly correlated. The convergent validity test with PLS software can be seen from the loading factor value for each construct indicator. Meanwhile, to assess convergent validity, the loading factor value must be more than 0.7, which is considered sufficient, whereas if it is greater than 0.7, it is said to be high, (Imam Ghozali, 2013:110) and the AVE (Average Variance Extracted) value must be greater than 0.7 with the following results:

Table 6: Loading factor validity test results

Variable Laten	Indicator Items	Loading Factor	AVE	Composite Reliability	Cronbach's Alpha
Halal Product	X1.1	0,752	0,549	0,830	0,728
	X1.2	0,722			
	X1.3	0,755			
	X1.4	0,735			
Green Marketing	X2.1	0,788	0,555	0,853	0,809
	X2.2	0,713			
	X2.3	0,703			
	X2.4	0,736			
	X2.5	0,736			
	X2.6	0,704			
	X2.7	0,731			
Information Adaption	X3.1	0,821	0,713	0,882	0,799
	X3.2	0,839			
	X3.3	0,874			
Purchase Decision	X4.1	0,729	0,536	0,810	0,718
	X4.2	0,786			
	X4.3	0,775			
	X4.4	0,771			
	X4.5	0,797			
	X4.6	0,745			
Customer Satisfaction	X5.1	0,732	0,596	0,855	0,774
	X5.2	0,788			
	X5.3	0,805			
	X5.4	0,761			
Customer Loyalty	Y.1	0,724	0,535	0,873	0,826
	Y.2	0,789			
	Y.3	0,723			
	Y.4	0,785			
	Y.5	0,795			
	Y.6	0,763			

Source: Results of data processing using SmartPLS (attached)

Based on Table 6, it can be seen that the results of the validity test prove that all the question items used to measure the variables in this research are Halal Product, Green Marketing, Information Adaptation, Purchase Decision, Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty have factor loading values greater than 0.70 (≥ 0.70) which means that all question items can be declared valid.

4.1.2.1 Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity is seen through measuring cross loading factors by comparing AVE and correlation between variables in a study. Discriminant validity can represent the extent to which a construct is empirically different from other constructs (Fornell and Lacker, 1981 in Ghazoli, 2014: 40). Fornell Lacker stated that a latent variable shares more variance with the underlying indicator than with other latent variables. If this is interpreted statistically, the AVE of each latent variable must be greater than the highest r^2 value with the value of the other latent variables. The second criterion for discriminant validity is that the "loading" for each indicator is expected to be higher than its respective "cross loading". If the Fornell Lacker assesses discriminant validity at the construct level (latent variable), then "cross-loading" is possible at the indicator level. Following is the validity test using the Fornell Lacker criterion test

Table 7: Discriminant Validity Test (Fornell Lacker Criterion)

	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	Y
X1	0,741					
X2	0,706	0,701				
X3	0,644	0,712	0,845			
X4	0,644	0,646	0,690	0,760		
X5	0,623	0,630	0,757	0,631	0,772	
Y	0,671	0,608	0,609	0,630	0,755	0,732

Source: SmartLS 4.0 data processing results, 2023

From the table above, it can be seen that the AVE root value of each latent variable is higher than the highest correlation value of that variable with other variables, so it can be concluded that the model has good discriminant validity.

Table 8: Heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT)

	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	Y
X1						
X2	0,815					
X3	0,555	0,387				
X4	0,837	0,763	0,816			
X5	0,84	0,832	0,197	0,569		
Y	0,869	0,74	0,424	0,68	0,826	

Source: Processed data (2023)

Based on Table 8, it was found that the HTMT value in this study was less than 0.90, so it can be concluded that this study has very good discriminant validity.

4.1.2.2 Reliability Test

Reliability testing is how far a measurement result on the same object can produce the same data. In Partial Least Square (PLS), reliability testing can use two methods, namely Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha. The value that must be met for each variable to be declared reliable is > 0.70 for the composite reliability value and > 0.70 for the Cronbach alpha value (Ghozali, 2014: 40). The following are the results of the reliability test using SmartPLS version 4.0 software:

4.1.3 Structural Model Testing (Inner Model)

The structural model (inner model) measurement aims to test the influence of other latent variables. The following are the results of bootstrapping in this research:

Figure 4: Inner Model

Source: SmartPLS Version 4.0 Output Results

Tests carried out on the inner model are based on path values to see whether the influence that can be displayed from the t-statistic value is significant or not. The t-statistic value can be obtained through the bootstrapping process in SmartPLS v4.0. To assess the significance of the prediction model in testing the structural model, it can be seen from the t-statistic value between the dependent variable and the mediator variable in the path coefficient table processed with SmartPLS in table 4.14 below.

4.1.3.1 Collinearity Test

Multicollinearity occurs when there are two or more independent variables in the regression analysis that have a strong relationship with each other. In this case, the variables cannot be considered completely independent, which may interfere with the interpretation of the results of the regression analysis. Multicollinearity is usually observed through statistical measurements such as correlation coefficients between independent variables (Hair et al., 2019).

Table 10: Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) Values

	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	Y
X1				2,151		
X2				2,011		
X3				1,257		
X4					1	
X5						1
Y						

Source: Data processed in 2023

Based on Table 10, it can be seen that the VIF value is <5, so this indicates that multicollinearity does not occur.

4.1.3.2 Path Coefficients and T Value

The boosting procedure in this research was carried out by applying the "bootstrapping" method to strengthen data analysis. Bootstrapping is a statistical technique used to generate a large number of repeated random samples from an existing dataset. It is useful in research to measure statistical uncertainty, estimate sampling distributions, and test hypotheses in a more robust way.

The t test is hypothesis testing. The significant values used (two-tailed) t-values were 1.65 (10% significant level), 1.96 (5% significant level) and 2.58 (1% significant level). In this study, researchers used an alpha level of 5% (two-way test). So the t table used is 1.96. To assess the significance of the prediction model in testing the structural model, it can be seen from the t-statistic value between the independent variable and the dependent variable in the path coefficient table in the SmartPLS output in table 4.14

4.1.3.3 R-Square

In testing the inner model, the R Square test is also carried out which is used to measure the level of variation in changes in the independent variable towards the dependent variable. The higher the R Square (R²) value means the better the prediction model and research model Abdillah and Hartono, (2015:197). Below are the values of R-Square in research processed using SmartPLS (v4.0)

Table 11: R Square Results (R2)

Variable	R Square
X4	0,669
X5	0,186
Y	0,571

Source: Data obtained (2023)

Table 11 shows that the R Square value for the Purchase Decision variable is 0.669 or 66.9% in the strong category influenced by halal products, green marketing and information adaptation. The R Square value of Customer Satisfaction is 0.186 or 18.6% in the weak category influenced by the Purchase decision variable and the R Square value of the Customer Loyalty variable is 0.571 or 57.1% in the strong category influenced by the Customer Satisfaction variable.

4.1.3.4 F-Square

Furthermore, in testing the inner model in this research, namely looking at the F-Square value, according to Ghoxali (2021:30) the F-Square value is 0.02, 0.15 and 0.35 for the late variable, which means that the latent variable is "weak.", Medium, or large for the dependent variable. The following are the F-Square results in this research.

Table 12: F-Square Results

Variable	F-Square
X1 -> X4	0,059
X2 -> X4	0,156
X3 -> X4	0,549
X4 -> X5	0,229
X5 -> Y	1,329

Source: Data obtained (2023)

Based on table 12, it can be stated as follows:

- a) The influence of Halal Products on Purchase Decisions is 0.059, which is included in the weak category.
- b) The influence of Green Marketing on Purchase Decisions is 0.156 which is included in the medium category
- c) The influence of Information Adaptation on Purchase Decision is 0.549 which is included in the large category.
- d) The influence of Purchase decisions on Customer Satisfaction is 0.229, which is included in the medium category
- e) The influence of Customer Satisfaction on Customer Loyalty is 1.329, which is included in the large category

4.1.3.5 Q-Square

Apart from looking at the large R-Square value, evaluating the results of the structural model can also be done using Q2 predictive relevance. The Q2 value > 0 indicates that the model has predictive relevance Ghozali, (2021:74). The following are the Q-Square results in this research which were processed in SmartPLS (v.3.2.9) via the Blinfoling procedure

Table 13: F-Square Results

Variable	SSO	SSE	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)
X1	1544	1544	
X2	2702	2702	
X3	1158	1158	
X4	2316	1655,076	0,285
X5	1544	1378,623	0,107
Y	2316	1633,961	0,294

Source: Data obtained (2023)

Based on the Q-Square results, it was found that the Purchase Decision, Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty variables had a Q-Square value > 0 so it could be concluded that this research model had predictive relevance.

4.2 Hypothesis Testing Results

Table 14: Path coefficient

Variable Laten	Original Sample	Sample Mean	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Values
Halal Preference (X ₁) -> Purchase Decision (X ₄)	0,204	0,200	0,052	3,943	0,000
Green Marketing (X ₂) -> Purchase Decision (X ₄)	0,322	0,320	0,051	6,351	0,000
Information Adaption (X ₁) -> Purchase Decision (X ₄)	0,478	0,483	0,046	10,439	0,000
Purchase Decision (X ₄) -> Customer Satisfaction (X ₅)	0,431	0,421	0,082	5,282	0,000
Customer Satisfaction (X ₅) -> Loyalitas Pelanggan (Y)	0,755	0,756	0,031	24,242	0,000

Source: Results of data processing with SmartPLS Version 4.0, 2023

4.2.1 The Influence of Halal Products on Purchase Decisions

To test the first hypothesis relating to the influence of Halal Products on Purchase Decisions, use the t-statistic values presented in table 4.14. Based on testing the t-statistical value for the green marketing variable on customer loyalty, it was obtained at 3.943 with the path coefficient formed being positive at 0.204. The t-statistic value is greater than the t-value (3.943) and the p-value (0.000) < 0.05 with the results having a significant effect. So it can be concluded that H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted, meaning that Halal Products have a significant effect on Purchase Decisions for Starbucks Coffee customers in Bandung. This is in line with research conducted by Anggadwita, Dini and Veland (2019) showing that the halal label significantly influences the product's brand image value.

4.2.2 The Influence of Green Marketing on Purchase Decisions

The second hypothesis tested is the influence of Green Marketing on Purchase Decisions, using the t-statistic values presented in table 4.14. Based on testing the t-statistical value for the service quality variable on customer loyalty, it was obtained at 6.351 with the path coefficient formed being positive at 0.322. The t-statistic value is greater than the t-value ($6.351 > 1.96$) and the p-value ($0.000 < 0.05$) with significant positive results. So it can be concluded that H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted, meaning that Green Marketing has a significant effect on Purchase Decisions for Starbucks Coffee customers in Bandung City. Dwipamurti et al. (2018) also show that green marketing has a positive effect on purchase decisions. Based on several previous studies, it is stated that there is a positive and significant relationship between green marketing and purchase decisions, so the research hypothesis proposed in the previous chapter is accepted

4.2.3 The Influence of Information Adaptation on Purchase Decisions

The third hypothesis tested is the influence of Information Adaption on Purchase Decesion using the t-statistic value presented in table 14. Based on testing the t-statistical value for the Information Adaption variable to Purchase Decession, it was obtained at 10.439 with the path coefficient formed being positive at 0.478. The t-statistic value is greater than the t-value ($10.439 > 1.96$) and the p-value ($0.000 < 0.05$). So it can be concluded that H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted, meaning that Information Adaption has a significant effect on Purchase Decesion. This is in line with research conducted by Shen, Zheng, and Zhao (2014) which states that Information Adaption has a significant effect on Purchase Decesion. Where the better the Information Adaption g, the better the Purchase Decree will be for Starbucks Coffee customers in Bandung City, so that the research hypothesis proposed in the previous chapter is accepted.

4.2.4 Influence of Purchase Decision on Customer Satisfaction

The fourth hypothesis tested is the influence of Purchase Decision on customer satisfaction using the t-statistic value presented in table 14. Based on testing the t-statistical value for the Purchase Decision variable on customer satisfaction, it was obtained at 5.282 with the path coefficient formed being positive at 0.431. The t-statistic value is greater than the t-value ($5.282 > 1.96$) and the p-value ($0.000 < 0.05$). So it can be concluded that H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted, meaning that the purchase decision has a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction. This is in line with research conducted by Kotler & Armstrong, (2018) which states that customer satisfaction is closely related to purchasing decisions.

4.2.5 The Influence of Customer Satisfaction on Customer Loyalty

The fifth hypothesis tested is the influence of customer satisfaction on customer loyalty, using the t-statistic value presented in table 4.23. Based on testing the t-statistical value for the customer satisfaction variable on customer loyalty, it was obtained at 24.242 with the path coefficient formed being positive at 0.755. The t-statistic value is greater than the t-value ($24.242 > 1.96$) and the p-value ($0.000 < 0.05$) with significant positive results. So it can be

concluded that H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted, meaning that customer satisfaction has a significant positive effect on customer loyalty. This is in line with research by Muhammad Hanif (2020) which states that customer satisfaction has a significant positive effect on customer loyalty. Where better customer satisfaction will be followed by better customer loyalty for Starbucks Coffee customers in Bandung City, so that the research hypothesis proposed in the previous chapter is accepted.

5. CONCLUSION

From the data found that Halal Products have a positive and significant effect on Purchase Decisions. Green marketing has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Decisions. Information Adaption has a positive and significant effect on Purchase. Purchase Decision has a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction. Customer Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Customer Loyalty among Starbucks Coffee customers in Bandung City.

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